

Angular losses in photovoltaic energy estimation: A review of models and a comparative analysis using the enhanced SISIFO simulation tool

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A detailed review of current models describing angular losses in photovoltaic modules.
- A review of the correction factors for diffuse irradiance in the literature.
- Simulation of different solar PV plants at different latitudes and two types of monofacial PV arrays: Static and horizontal single-axis with activated back-tracking.
- Implementation of Incidence Angle Modifier models in open source software for front and rear faces of PV modules.
- Providing the user with a new simulation tool to quantify more accurately the refractive losses associated with PV modules.
- Annual energy losses in percentage terms are between 1 % and 5 % depending on the model being used to simulate clean modules.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
 PV simulation
 Open-source
 IAM
 Correction factors
 Annual energy losses

ABSTRACT

The modeling of the optical losses in PV modules when the angle of incidence is greater than zero (referred to as IAM, for “Incidence Angle Modifier”) has been reviewed. Six different models of IAM, have been described, including (a) the primary directional formulation applicable to the direct irradiance and (b) the derived correction factors for the diffuse irradiance components reflected from the sky and from the ground (for front and rear irradiance). The methodology followed consisted of the modification of SISIFO, an open and free PV software, through the implementation of the six IAM models. This was followed by an extensive simulation exercise, extended to static and tracked PV arrays in three different latitudes, carried out aiming to understand the impact of the IAM losses and the compatibility between the different IAM models. This allows the software improvement to be validated with real PV plants to reduce the uncertainty in the annual energy calculation. Other software such as PVsyst uses the Fresnel model, based on Fresnel’s laws applied to the air-glass interface. This model considers the increase in refractive index of the encapsulation materials from the air to the PV cell. However, other

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116377>

Received 31 March 2025; Received in revised form 1 September 2025; Accepted 7 October 2025

Available online 22 October 2025

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models offer some advantages in mathematical handling, which have been implemented in this paper. The basis for IAM model parameters was proposed for bare-glass and AR-coated PV modules. Annual losses across models matched within $\pm 0.2\%$, ensuring consistent accuracy in all cases. Annual energy losses are between 1 % and 5 % depending on the model being used to simulate.

Nomenclature	
$1 \times p$	One-axis tracker with axis parallel to ground and other tracker axes
AAL	Annual angular losses
AM	Air mass
AOI	Angle of incidence
AR	Antireflective coating cell
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-conditioning Engineers
a_0, \dots, a_1	Parameters of the SANDIA Model
a_t	Dimensionless main parameter of the analytical version of the Martín-Ruiz Model
b_0	Parameter of the ASHRAE Model
B	Direct (beam) in-plane irradiance
B_a	Annual direct (beam) radiation
c_1, c_2	Parameters for some AOI correction factors in the analytical version of the Martín-Ruiz Model
D	Diffuse irradiance
D_a	Annual diffuse radiation
D^{CIR}	Circumsolar diffuse irradiance
D^{HB}	Horizontal brightening diffuse irradiance
D^{ISO}	Isotropic diffuse irradiance
EVA	Ethylene-vinyl-acetate
F	Angle-of-incidence correction factor
G^*	Global irradiance at STC
G_a	Annual global radiation
G_R	Global irradiance at the PV module backside
GCR	Ground coverage ratio
IAM	Incidence angle modifier
IAM^A	IAM absorption in the cover glass
IAM^R	IAM reflection losses at the first interface
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
K	Glass extinction coefficient
L	Glass thickness
n	Refractive index
n_{PYR}	Refractive index of the pyranometer
P	Power
POE	Polyolefin elastomers
PV	Photovoltaic
R^{ground}	Reflected irradiance from the ground
R^{row}	Reflected irradiance from the back row
R^2	Coefficient of determination
R^U	Reflection coefficient of unpolarized light
R^P	Reflection coefficient of p-polarized light
R^S	Reflection coefficient of s-polarized light
R_a	Annual reflected radiation
RES	Residual function
S	Sample of θ values
SISIFO	Software for simulating PV systems
STC	Standard Test Conditions
T	Transmission coefficient
β	Tilt of the PV module (row)
β_{HS}	Sky angle that is hidden by the preceding row
Γ	Parameter of the Eye-sensitivity Model
ρ	Ground Reflectivity
θ	Angle of incidence, AOI
θ_T	Angle of transmission (refraction)
w	Weighting function
<i>subscripts</i>	
F	Front
R	Rear
a	Annual
E	Experimental
M	Modeled
<i>subscripts</i>	
*	Under Standard Test Conditions

1. Introduction

When applying to photovoltaic (PV) modules, it is important to note that normal incidence losses are already included in the definition of power under standard test conditions (STC), P^* while also considering G^* as global in-plane irradiance at STC (1000 W/m^2). Incidence Angle Modifier, IAM, refers to additional optical losses that occur when the angle between the incident light on a surface and the normal to the surface, θ , is not zero. Leaving aside other effects of spectrum and temperature, which are different issues from the one at hand, the power at a direct in-plane irradiance, B , can be written as:

$$P(B) = P^* \frac{B}{G^*} IAM(\theta) \tag{1}$$

with

$$IAM(\theta) = \frac{T(\theta)}{T(0)} \tag{2}$$

where T is the transmission coefficient, defined as the ratio between the irradiance transmitted to the solar cells and the incident irradiance. It depends on the angle of incidence.

IAM loss is caused by two different reasons. First, in perfectly clean PV modules, there are reflection losses due to changes in the optical properties of materials as light passes from the air to the solar cells through the stack of materials that make up the PV modules. Secondly, in dirty modules, the volumetric properties of dust lead to additional IAM losses [1–3]. In rigor, IAM in clean modules is also governed by absorption losses on the PV module cover glass and encapsulant, which depend on the path length of the light through these materials, which in turn depends on the angle of incidence. However, the effect of absorption on IAM losses is negligible in practice. Depending on the PV array geometry, as well as the prevailing solar radiation and soiling conditions, annual IAM losses, usually referred to as Annual Angular Losses (AAL), represent between 1 % and 5 % of the yearly energy yield in utility-scale PV plants. This is large enough to be taken into account when modeling the yield.

Earlier PV modules, say before 2017, were typically covered by bare glass, so the corresponding IAM reflection losses can be modeled by successively applying Fresnel's laws to the multiple interfaces (air-glass-encapsulant – antireflective (AR) coating cell-cell) through which the light must pass. In principle, this multiplicity of interfaces entails significant mathematical complexity. Therefore, non-Fresnel

alternatives have been considered, either purely empirical or derived from mathematical treatment of the Fresnel equations. However, since all the internal interfaces of the PV module are designed to minimize reflection (which is why PV modules look very dark), it is generally sufficient to consider only the first interface (air glass) for practical purposes. Bare glass reflects around 4 % of the light incident perpendicular to the air-glass interface. To reduce this reflection, the addition of AR coatings to the glass has become the standard solution in modern PV modules. AR coatings also reduce reflectance over a wide range of θ , thus minimizing IAM losses. Modern AR coatings are based on quarter-wave interfaces or subwavelength nanostructures [4,5], and the Fresnel law cannot be applied to these non-homogeneous materials. Instead, IAM can be obtained experimentally and the corresponding results, in the form of a list of pairs of $[\theta_E, IAM_E]$ values where the subindex “E” means experimental, can be used directly for IAM modeling in energy yield estimation software. PV module manufacturers usually provide a few pairs of values in some format (e.g. in .pan files).

However, the use of .pan files leads to interpolation for θ values other than θ_E in the provided pairs of values. Therefore, it is useful to look for other models that are able to directly provide IAMs for all θ values in the range of 0° – 90° . One possibility is to use models based on Fresnel equations but with parameters different from those used for bare glass PV modules. For example, PVsyst proposes to deal directly with bare glass and AR coated PV modules using the Fresnel equations, but with different values of the refractive index, n , being $n = 1.526$ and $n = 1.29$ the proposed values for bare glass and AR coated glass, respectively.

In this article, IAM modeling is first reviewed by describing several proposals from the available literature using the same notation. Our aim is to apply them in the context of photovoltaic energy yield estimation, so we need not only to treat the direct component of irradiance, which most models provide, but also to propose a treatment for the other components of irradiance (diffuse and reflected). Secondly, by adding these models to SISIFO, a free software tool for estimating energy yield, an extensive simulation exercise is carried out on the performance of static and single-axis tracking PV generators at three sites with different latitudes. The use of photovoltaic simulation software allows solar systems to be sized with high accuracy and minimal uncertainty, optimizing the performance and economic viability of large installations. To achieve truly reliable estimates of energy production, it is essential to use advanced IAM models, as they more accurately represent the actual behaviour and angular losses experienced by PV modules in the field. This makes it possible to evaluate and compare the quantitative impact of each model, the adjustment parameters proposed for each model, and, finally, to analyze the sensitivity of the irradiance estimates to the parameters of each model. It is worth mentioning in advance that clean modules are considered, as only one of the reviewed models takes into account the additional effect of soiling.

The IAM issue is not exclusive to the PV modules but also affects any kind of solar devices. In fact, the open literature includes specific papers on other solar devices [6,7]. It is important to mention that because of the specific characteristics of each device, the corresponding solutions are of little use for photovoltaic modules.

2. Review of IAM models

The development of IAM models can be traced back to the pioneering work of Dutch astronomer and mathematician Willebrord Snel circa 1621. Snel experimentally discovered the foundational equation that elucidates the relationship between the angle of incidence, θ , and the angle of transmission (or refraction), θ_T , as light transits between two isotropic media with different refractive indices, n_1 and n_2 Fig. 1-Left. This seminal discovery laid the groundwork for understanding the behavior of light at the interface of materials with distinct optical properties.

$$n_1 \sin \theta = n_2 \sin \theta_T \tag{3}$$

Fig. 1. (Left) Angles of incidence and transmission at the smooth interface between two layers of homogeneous materials with different refractive indices. (Right) Multiple reflections through the stack of different materials composing a PV module.

Nearly three centuries later, French physicist Augustin Fresnel advanced the understanding of the behavior of light by proposing that light waves are purely transverse in nature. Fresnel’s work elucidated the phenomenon of polarization and provided mathematical equations for determining reflectance and transmittance at smooth interfaces between thick layers of different materials. These contributions greatly enhanced the theoretical framework for light-matter interactions. The reflectance (or power reflection coefficient) of s-polarized and p-polarized light is, respectively:

$$R^S(\theta) = \left(\frac{n_1 \cos \theta - n_2 \cos \theta_T}{n_1 \cos \theta + n_2 \cos \theta_T} \right)^2 \tag{4}$$

and

$$R^P(\theta) = \left(\frac{n_1 \cos \theta_T - n_2 \cos \theta}{n_1 \cos \theta_T + n_2 \cos \theta} \right)^2 \tag{5}$$

The reflectance of unpolarized light, which is the case of the light hitting on the PV modules:

$$R^U(\theta) = \frac{R^S(\theta) + R^P(\theta)}{2} \tag{6}$$

Therefore, the transmittance (or power transmission coefficient) of unpolarized light is

$$T^U(\theta) = 1 - R^U(\theta) \tag{7}$$

In principle, the transmittance from the air to the cell through the stack of layers of the constituent materials of a PV module can be analyzed by ray-tracing, taking into account the reflectance at the different interfaces and the multiple reflections illustrated in Fig. 1-Right (the layers are illuminated by light reflected from the subsequent layer). The reflection in thick layers compared to the wavelength of the spectra of interest (glass and EVA/POE encapsulation) is calculated using the Fresnel equations, while for thin layers (the AR coatings) the interference must be considered using the matrix method [8] and the wavelength dependence of the refractive indices. In fact, such detailed models, even considering other PV module features (metallization patterns, intercell gap, cell-frame gap, etc.) have been developed mainly for the purpose of PV module design studies. However, these models are of little use for general energy yield simulation, because they are complex to use and require input data to define the constitution of the PV module, which are generally not available. The PV module can have a multiplicity of successive interfaces that are relevant in terms of refractive losses. In practice, this multiplicity significantly increases the mathematical complexity of modeling panel behavior and describing experimental testing results. That has led to long research and proposals for alternative, simpler models. All IAM models are shown in Table 1. In chronological order:

2.1. The ASHRAE model

Modeling and standard testing of solar collectors began in the 1960s with thermal (not PV) panels. Even a simple double-glazed thermal model has four air-glass interfaces, so there was a need for an IAM model with mathematical complexity appropriate to the computing resources available more than 50 years ago. In 1966, a simple IAM (θ) equation was proposed [9] to overcome this problem.

$$IAM(\theta) = 1 - b_0 \left(\frac{1}{\cos \theta} \right) \tag{8}$$

where b_0 is a parameter fitted from empirical data. This equation was later (1977) adopted by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) [10] and has become very popular, despite suffering from a discontinuity at $\theta = 90^\circ$ and a low accuracy at high incident angles. Some authors suggest not using this function for $\theta > 80^\circ$ [11].

Approximately two decades later, PV modules became mature industrial products, also requiring standard modeling and testing. Understandably, the ASHRAE model was initially adopted for PV modules. For example, it was used by PVSyst in its early days in 1992. However, the different nature of thermal panels and PV modules motivated the revision of IAM modeling for energy yield estimation, leading to new proposals more specific to PV modules.

2.2. The air-glass model

It was soon realized that the transmittance relative to normal incidence is dominated by the air-glass interface [12] because as the refractive index of the encapsulation material increases, the light entering the glass cover layer has an angular distribution within a cone of about 42° ($\theta = 85^\circ$, $n_1 = 1$ and $n_2 = 1.52$ in Eq. (3) gives $\theta_T = 41^\circ$) and this relatively small range of angles of incidence at the subsequent interfaces results in little change in transmittance after the air-glass interface. In addition, the dispersion due to the spectral dependence of the refractive index in the relevant bandwidth for Si cells (400–1200 nm) is very small, so it is appropriate to use only one value (typically corresponding to 800 nm) for the entire bandwidth. This led in 1996 to the development of an IAM model based on only the air-glass interface and a single n value [13]. Basic mathematical handling of Eqs. (2)–(7), leads to

$$IAM(\theta) = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sin^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\sin^2(\theta_T + \theta)} + \frac{\tan^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\tan^2(\theta_T + \theta)} \right]}{1 - \left(\frac{n_1 - n_2}{n_1 + n_2} \right)^2} \tag{9}$$

The simplest IAM air-glass model is to apply this equation for $n_1 = 1$ (air) and $n_2 = 1.526$ or $n_2 = 1.29$, the commonly used default values for bare glass or AR-coated glass, respectively. In the first paper to develop this [13], published in the days when the cover was just bare glass, one can read: "...the air-glass model is not more complicated than the ASHRAE model, gives a very good fit to measured data and is based on optical formulas without adjustable parameters. Therefore, we recommend using the air-glass model instead of ASHRAE as a standard model for practical calculations". PVSyst has followed this recommendation from version 6.6 in 2017. This software even allows extending this model to consider two consecutive interfaces: air-AR layer ($n_1 = 1$ and $n_2 = 1.29$) and AR layer-glass ($n_1 = 1.29$ and $n_2 = 1.526$). However, the practical impact of this refinement is very low.

2.3. The Martín-Ruiz model

In 2001, Martín and Ruiz [14–16] proposed the equation:

$$IAM(\theta) = 1 - \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\cos \theta}{a_r}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{a_r}\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{a_r}\right)} \tag{10}$$

where a_r is an empirical dimensionless parameter, called the angular losses coefficient. It is worth mentioning that the first paper [17] that

Table 1
Summary of IAM models in the literature.

Names	IAM model	Parameters
ASHRAE	$1 - b_0 \left(\frac{1}{\cos \theta} \right)$	b_0
Air-glass	$1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sin^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\sin^2(\theta_T + \theta)} + \frac{\tan^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\tan^2(\theta_T + \theta)} \right]$	n_1, n_2
Martín-Ruiz	$1 - \frac{1 - \left(\frac{n_1 - n_2}{n_1 + n_2} \right)^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\cos \theta}{a_r}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{a_r}\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{a_r}\right)}$	a_r
Sandia	$a_0 + a_1 \theta + a_2 \theta^2 + a_3 \theta^3 + a_4 \theta^4 + a_5 \theta^5$	$a_0 \dots a_5$
Physical	$\frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sin^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\sin^2(\theta_T + \theta)} + \frac{\tan^2(\theta_T - \theta)}{\tan^2(\theta_T + \theta)} \right] \right) \exp\left(-\frac{KL}{\cos \theta_T}\right)}{\left(1 - \left(\frac{n_1 - n_2}{n_1 + n_2} \right)^2 \right) \exp(-KL)}$	K
Eye-sensitivity	$1 - \Gamma^{(\theta - 90^\circ)}$	Γ

presented this model did so as if it were purely empirical, without any relation to optical formulas. This paper only says: "...with the aim of finding simple analytical expressions that describe the angular performance of the PV modules weighted and after observing the behavior of the reflectance curves". However, more detailed information lets know that in fact the model results essentially from the first terms of the Taylor series of the function obtained by applying the Fresnel equations to a successive chain of interfaces. This helps explain why the IAM(θ) curves resulting from Eqs. (9) and (10) are practically indistinguishable, given the proper choice of a_r and n values. In particular, $a_r = 0.17$ and $a_r = 0.14$ are consistent with $n = 1.526$ and $n = 1.29$.

An advantage of the Martín-Ruiz model over the Air-glass model is that it allows one to derive analytical expressions for the AOI correction factor for irradiance components other than direct. This model has been widely referenced in the literature (454 references in Google Scholar as of March 21, 2025) and is specifically recommended in IEC 61,853-2 [18] for describing the corresponding IAM experimental results.

This paper is focused on IAM in perfectly clean modules. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the authors of this model state that the increase in IAM losses due to soiling can be modeled by increasing the value of a_r as in another study that considers the Martín-Ruiz equations to analyse the soiling energy losses in PV plants [19]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the only model published to date that allows this effect to be incorporated into energy yield estimation software.

2.4. The Sandia model

In 2004, SANDIA [20] proposed the use of a fifth-order polynomial equation to model a commercial PV module

$$IAM(\theta) = a_0 + a_1 \theta + a_2 \theta^2 + a_3 \theta^3 + a_4 \theta^4 + a_5 \theta^5 \tag{11}$$

where the coefficients (a_0, \dots, a_5) are determined by fitting its experimental data. An extensive testing campaign carried out at SANDIA, covering a large part of the commercial modules of the time, fed a publicly available coefficients database; This model was implemented in the SAM software tool [21] and experienced a certain boom in the decade following its publication. However, the use of a fifth-order polynomial leads to intrinsic model drawbacks. On the one hand, up to six coefficients are needed to describe the IAM curves, while other models require only one. On the other hand, this causes the model to exhibit some nonphysical features [22]: a slightly concave-up shape at low angles of incidence, IAM(θ) values greater than 1 for this range ($\theta < 40^\circ$) and values greater than 0 for $\theta = 90^\circ$. Today, the SANDIA database is no longer supported, and this model is considered deprecated [23].

2.5. The physical model

In 2006, De Soto, Klein, and Beckman proposed what is often referred to as the Physical model [24]. This model considers IAM losses as the

the ground seen by the PV array

$$F_{R,F} = \frac{\int_{\varphi=0}^{\varphi=2\pi} \int_{\theta=0}^{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} \text{IAM}(\theta) \cos \theta d\varphi d\theta}{\int_{\varphi=0}^{\varphi=2\pi} \int_{\theta=0}^{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos \theta d\varphi d\theta} \quad (19)$$

And $F_{HB,F}$ for light from the horizon band

$$F_{HB,F} = \frac{\int_{\varphi=0}^{\varphi=2\pi} \text{IAM}(\theta_{\varphi}^L) \cos \theta_{\varphi}^L d\varphi}{\int_{\varphi=0}^{\varphi=2\pi} \cos \theta_{\varphi}^L d\varphi} \quad (20)$$

It is worth noting that all these AOI correction factors are in fact independent of the site and of the PV plant configuration or layout, so that they can be handled as universal bidimensional functions depending on an angle (θ for $F_{B,F}$, and β for $F_{D,F}$, $F_{HB,F}$ and $F_{R,F}$) and on the IAM model parameter. Fig. 3 shows the corresponding maps for the air-glass model, considering the parameter range $1.1 \leq n \leq 1.7$, which easily covers all known experimental values. Similar maps can be generated for other one-parameter IAM models. As a result of this work, we provided them at [Open Access](#).

3.2. Rear irradiance

Fig. 4-Left shows the rear irradiance components at the center of the rear of an inner row of a multirow PV array on flat terrain: beam, B_R , reflected from the ground, R_R^{ground} , reflected by the back row, R_R^{row} , and isotropic diffuse from a portion of the sky, D_R^{ISO} . Analogous to Eq. (15), the AOI-corrected in-plane rear irradiance is given by:

$$G_R^{\text{AOI}} = F_{B,R} B_R + F_{D,R} D_R^{\text{ISO}} + F_{RR,R} R_R^{\text{row}} + F_{RR,R} R_R^{\text{ground}} \quad (21)$$

where $F_{B,R}$, $F_{D,R}$, $F_{RR,R}$, and $F_{RR,R}$ are the corresponding AOI correction factors. In the last row of a multirow PV array, the term $F_{RR,R} R_R^{\text{row}}$ is replaced by the horizon irradiance component as seen from the rear. In principle, these factors can be calculated in the same way as for Eqs. (19) and (20). It is worth mentioning that the here implemented G_R calculation method is in coherence to the one described in [27] but neglecting the specular reflected component. This is equivalent to considering the soil as a Lambertian reflector, which is the case for most natural grounds [28].

3.3. Calculation issues for multirow PV arrays

The non-uniformity of the irradiance emitted by the ground which in turn is a consequence of (a) the succession of shaded and unshaded areas due to the arrangement of the rows in multirow PV arrays [29] (represented in Fig. 4 by the succession of thin and thick segments in the ground line) and (b) the different isotropic diffuse irradiance at each ground point due to its different view of the sky (rows shade the sky), makes the AOI correction factor calculation more complex in practice.

A simple and reasonable approximation is obtained by ignoring such non-uniformity and assuming that the reflection from the ground is isotropic. Then $F_{R,R}$ becomes equal to $F_{D,F}$, as given by Eq. (18) and Fig. 4-Right presents a schematic representation of the view factors seen by the front and rear faces of a bifacial module and helps to understand that the view factor from the sky to the front face is equal to the view factor of the ground to the rear face. Furthermore, the rationality of this approximation is supported by the fact that G_R^{AOI} is generally much lower than G_F^{AOI} , making the impact of the approximation in the estimate of the energy yield very small. An additional argument in favor of understanding this approximation is that the difference between the observed values of the effective albedo (irradiance from the ground measured with a reference cell; thus, already AOI corrected) and the global albedo (irradiance from the ground measured with a pyranometer) is typically low [30]. Similar reasons lead to approximating $F_{RR,R}$ and $F_{D,R}$ by $F_{R,F}$.

A more accurate approach is to integrate IAM(θ) for each shaded or unshaded ground band seen, as is done with the horizon band, and aggregate the results, taking into account that the global ground irradiance

Fig. 3. Two-dimensional maps of the AOI correction factor for each of the four components of the frontal irradiance when using the Air-glass model.

is different for each ground band due to the issue of diffuse irradiance mentioned above. Reducing the size of the ground bands considered improves the accuracy of the calculation.

In addition, some PV software is able to calculate the irradiance at each point of the row; in this case, especially for sloping terrain, different situations may occur at each point; for example, some higher row points may see the horizon band while lower points do not. This only leads to a different calculation of the irradiance components for each point due to different view factors from the ground and from the sky, implying different integration limits in Eqs. (18) and (19). The same solution could be applied to consider horizon shading, sometimes called

Fig. 4. Three components of the rear irradiance in the center of a row of a multirow PV array (Left). View factors seen by the front and rear faces of a bifacial module (Right).

far shading, since the known horizon height for each φ could be applied as the integration limit for φ in Eqs. (18) and (19).

In any case, the validity of the models presented is not affected by these additional calculation details required for multirow PV arrays, sloping terrain, or other issues.

3.4. Review of angle-of-incidence correction factors in the literature

For some AOI correction factors, analytical (or numerical) solutions are available as alternatives to the general case presented above, allowing for a reduction in computational effort and time. In chronological order of publication:

3.4.1. Martín-Ruiz, 2001

In 2001, the original publication of the Martín-Ruiz [15] already contained approximate analytical equations for $F_{D,F}$ and $F_{R,F}$. These are:

$$F_{D,F}(\beta) \approx \exp \left[-\frac{1}{a_r} \left(c_1 \left(\sin \beta + \frac{\pi - \beta - \sin \beta}{1 + \cos \beta} \right) + c_2 \left(\sin \beta + \frac{\pi - \beta - \sin \beta}{1 + \cos \beta} \right)^2 \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

And

$$F_{R,F}(\beta) \approx \exp \left[-\frac{1}{a_r} \left(c_1 \left(\sin \beta + \frac{\beta - \sin \beta}{1 - \cos \beta} \right) + c_2 \left(\sin \beta + \frac{\beta - \sin \beta}{1 - \cos \beta} \right)^2 \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

where β is the tilt of the PV module and c_1, c_2 are adjusted parameters. Recommended default values are:

$$c_1 = \frac{4}{3\pi}, \quad c_2 = 0.4544 \cdot a_r - 0.1459. \quad (24)$$

These authors do not provide an analytical expression for $F_{HB,F}$. However, the practical significance of this omission is very small because D_F^{HB} is typically very low and because in multirow PV arrays on flat terrain this irradiance component is hidden by the preceding row.

3.4.2. Marion, 2017

In 2017, a numerical method for solving the integrals in Eqs. (18)–(20) is given in [31]. It is worth noting that these authors also use spherical polar coordinates but with respect to location, i.e., with the Y and Z axes pointing south and zenith, respectively. Marion [31] also proposes 5th order polynomials as a substitute for performing the numerical solutions of Eqs. (18)–(20) for the Air-glass model but only in the case of $n = 1.526$ (generic uncoated glass) or $n = 1.29$ (generic

AR-coated glass). For example:

$$F_{D,F}(\beta, n = 1.526) \approx 9.4487 \times 10^{-1} + 3.4581 \times 10^{-4} \beta + 1.8524 \times 10^{-5} \beta^2 - 7.0766 \times 10^{-7} \beta^3 + 8.1577 \times 10^{-9} \beta^4 - 3.3904 \times 10^{-11} \beta^5 \quad (25)$$

for $n = 1.526$ case, where β is expressed in sexagesimal degrees.

3.4.3. Wright, 2019

In 2019, a closed-form analytical solution for $F_{D,F}$ was derived for the ASHRAE model [32]. Translated into the notation of this paper, it is:

$$F_{D,F}(\beta) = \left[1 + b_0 - \frac{4b_0}{1 + \cos \beta} + \frac{4b_0 \beta}{\pi(1 + \cos \beta)} \right] \quad (26)$$

3.4.4. Xie, 2022

In 2022, analytical solutions for $F_{D,F}$ and $F_{R,F}$ derived from integrals of an alternative form of the Fresnel equations [33] were proposed. They are given by:

$$F_{D,F} = \frac{2w}{\pi(1 + \cos \beta)} \left[\frac{30}{7} \pi - \frac{160}{21} \beta - \frac{10}{3} \pi \cos \beta + \frac{160}{21} \cos \beta \sin \beta - \frac{5}{3} \pi \cos \beta \sin^2 \beta + \frac{20}{7} \cos \beta \sin^3 \beta - \frac{5}{16} \pi \cos \beta \sin^4 \beta + \frac{16}{105} \cos \beta \sin^5 \beta \right] \quad (27)$$

$$F_{R,F} = \frac{40w}{21(1 - \cos \beta)} - \frac{(1 + \cos \beta)}{(1 - \cos \beta)} F_{D,F} \quad (28)$$

where β is in radians and where w is a weighting function used by the alternative Fresnel equations that reflects the variation of the relative transmittance with the refractive index of the PV cover and is given by

$$w(n) = \frac{n(n_{PYR} + 1)^2}{n_{PYR}(n + 1)^2} \left[2.77526 \times 10^{-9} + 3.74953n - 5.18527n^2 + 3.41186n^3 - 1.08794n^4 - 0.13606n^5 \right] \quad (29)$$

where n_{PYR} is the refractive index of the pyranometer used to measure the global incident in-plane irradiance and n is the refractive index of the PV cover. Typically, such an instrument is covered by a fused silica dome, resulting in a perpendicular incidence of diffuse irradiance on the inner cell. So far, this model has been used to explain the discrepancy between irradiance observations using a pyranometer and a reference photovoltaic cell.

4. Obtaining the IAM model parameter

4.1. Fitting to the experimental IAM curve

The straightforward alternative to derive the fitting coefficients of the different IAM models is to fit the models directly to the experimental IAM curves. For this purpose, we applied the Gauss-Newton least-squares fitting, which minimizes the sum of the squared differences between the modeled and experimental values. In other words, we considered a residual function RES, defined as

$$RES = \sum_{\theta \in S} (IAM_M(\theta) - IAM_E(\theta))^2 \quad (30)$$

where the sub-indexes M and E refer to modeled and experimental, respectively, and S is the sample of available θ values in the experimental

θ_E	IAM _E
0	1
5	1
10	1
15	1.001
20	1
25	1.001
30	0.999
35	0.999
40	0.995
45	0.991
50	0.983
55	0.971
60	0.952
65	0.921
70	0.871
75	0.790
80	0.660
85	0.469
90	0

Fig. 5. (Left) Average values for bare glass encapsulated cells tested in a round-robin by 12 international laboratories. (Right) The evolution of the RES and R^2 versus the corresponding fitting model parameters.

report. Then, we searched for the IAM model parameter that leads to the minimum of RES, and we analyzed the goodness of fit using the coefficient of determination, R^2 , calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{\theta \in S} (IAM_E(\theta) - IAM_M(\theta))^2}{\sum_{\theta \in S} (IAM_E(\theta) - \overline{IAM_E})^2} \quad (31)$$

As a representative example, Fig. 5 shows the evolution of RES as a function of the fitting parameter for the ASHRAE Eq. (8), Air-glass Eq. (9), Martín-Ruiz Eq. (10), and Eye-sensitivity Eq. (14) models for the case of an experimental curve given in [25]. The parameter ranges tested were: $0.007 \leq b_0 \leq 0.07$; $1.1 \leq n \leq 1.7$; $0.11 \leq a_r \leq 0.18$; $1.10 \leq \Gamma \leq 1.16$. It is worth noting about this experimental curve that: (a) it has been derived from values obtained during an extensive interlaboratory comparison of IAM measurements on encapsulated PV cells conducted in 12 international laboratories [34] and (b) the tested PV module samples are covered by bare glass from two different manufacturers and include three different Si solar cell technologies; this suggests that it can be considered as representative of bare-glass modules.

The result of this exercise is rather disappointing. It is observed that the curves are quite flat near the minimum, which makes parameter optimization difficult. This is particularly true for the air-glass model. For example, the absolute minimum of RES for this model occurs at $n = 1.385$, which seems very different from $n = 1.526$, which is widely accepted as representative for bare glass modules. In fact, the RES corresponding to both values are very similar, 0.003 and 0.005, respectively. Moreover, the parameters corresponding to the absolute minimum of RES depend on the choice of S .

The background to this issue is the relatively low sensitivity of IAM curves to n . This can be seen in Fig. 6, where the experimental curve of this example is plotted together with the modeled curves for $n = 1.1$ and $n = 1.7$. The corresponding R^2 and RES versus n are given in Fig. 5 right. It is observed that in the range of $n = 1.3$ to 1.4 there is a margin of interest by being above $R^2 = 0.997$. Consistently, the sensitivity of the angular losses to n is also low. This is discussed further in the next section. It is worth reporting that we also tried to fit by minimizing the sum of the absolute (not squared) differences, but the optimization difficulty persists.

This low sensitivity of energy losses to model parameters, together with the relative homogeneity of the encapsulation materials of today's PV modules, supports the use of default representative values for estimating PV energy yield. The widely accepted values are $n = 1.526$ and $n = 1.259$ for bare glass and AR-coated glass modules, respectively.

Other authors have mentioned similar optimization difficulties [35] for the ASHRAE model. We suspect that this difficulty may be a relevant reason why IEC 61853 [18] specifically recommends the Martín-Ruiz model to fit the experimental IAM curves.

An interesting aspect is the validity of the IAM experimental values provided by the manufacturers for the new generations of modules. For example, for a CHSM72M(DG)-540Wp module the experimental values available in the pan file correspond to a parameter $a_r = 0.051$ in the Martín-Ruiz model Fig. 7. This is an extremely low parameter value. The validity of this value for new modules and its possible degradation over the lifetime of the module are left for further study. As a reference of the relevance of this parameter, in a typical plant in Madrid-Spain ($1 \times p$), going from $a_r = 0.14$ (as a reference for modules with AR layer) to $a_r = 0.051$ means going from $AAL = 1.53\%$ to $AAL = 0.23\%$, respectively.

Fig. 6. IAM curves for $n = 1.1$ (blue line); $n = 1.7$ (yellow line) and experimental (red line).

Fig. 7. Evolution of the RES and R^2 for CHSM72M(DG)-540Wp.

4.2. Inter-model parameter translation

On the other hand, keeping in mind the estimation of PV energy yield, it should be noted that the total angular losses along a given time period essentially result from the product of two functions: the selected IAM (θ) model and the distribution of in-plane irradiance versus θ , which in turn depends on the case, i.e., a given location (latitude and solar climate), a given PV array design (tracker strategy and geometry) and a given time period. In principle, for a given case, it should be possible to choose a set of model parameters that result in the same IAM losses. This idea can be of practical interest to the extent that parameter transfer relations (i.e. for deriving the parameters of one model from the parameters of another model) can be considered universal, that is, applicable to all the cases. That has been explored by SANDIA in 2023 for the ASHRAE Eq. (8), Martín-Ruiz Eq. (10) and the Physical Eq. (12) models, under

Fig. 8. Relationship between the angles ($\beta + \beta_{HS}$) considering a front row of photovoltaic modules.

the assumption that the annual distribution of the irradiance versus θ is always proportional to $(1 - \sin \theta)$, that is, $\cos \theta$. This study [36] has led to the proposal of transfer polynomial functions, which allow converting the parameters of a source model to the parameters of a target model. For example, for the Martín-Ruiz model to be equivalent to the Physical model with $L = 0$, the corresponding equations are

$$a_r(n) = \frac{4.915 \times 10^{-5}}{n - 0.9702} - 4.1071 + 10.679n - 10.134n^2 + 4.319n^3 - 0.69491n^4$$

$$b_0(n) = \frac{-0.231}{-70.19n + 59.6} - 0.5265 + 0.8787n - 0.4568n^2 + 0.0799n^3 \quad (32)$$

Analogously, for the Physical model with $L = 0$ to be equivalent to the Martín-Ruiz model

$$n(a_r) = 2.904 - 65.99a_r + 843.2a_r^2 - 4615a_r^3 + 9553a_r^4$$

$$b_0(a_r) = 0.004534 + 0.08397a_r - 5.349a_r^2 + 57.129a_r^3 - 1239a_r^4 \quad (33)$$

Note that these equations are not exactly mutually equivalent. For example, for $n = 1.526$, Eq. (32) leads to $a_r = 0.16985 \pm 0.002$, which, with Eq. (33) leads to $n = 1.358 \pm 0.0015$. Again, this reflects the inherent difficulties of optimizing the parameters of the IAM model. However, while a difference of 11 % in n may seem very significant, the corresponding difference in energy yield is not high. For example, for a single-axis tracking PV plant in Chile, the annual angular losses corresponding to these two n values are 0.97 % and 0.84 %, respectively. That is, the difference in the final energy yield is less than 0.2 % (the details of the calculation are given in the next section). We therefore believe that these conversion equations retain their validity.

Moreover, note that these conversion equations were derived from a strictly mathematical perspective, considering fitting ranges for the parameters that are much wider than the required ones. For example, the allowable range for n in the referenced SANDIA study was $1 < n < 2$, while the expected range is $1.22 < n < 1.53$, that is, from the target refractive index to the bare glass one. We suspect that restricting the study to this expected real range may lead to best-fit coefficients in Eqs. (32)

Table 2

Solar climate characteristics of the three analyzed sites and geometric features of the PV plants considered in this paper. $G_a(0)$ and $D_a(0)$ are the mean annual global and diffuse horizontal radiation, respectively, and ρ , β and GCR mean ground reflectivity (albedo), tilt and ground coverage ratio, respectively.

Country	Latitude	$G_a(0)$ [kWh/m ²]	$\frac{D_a(0)}{G_a(0)}$	ρ	β	GCR (static)	GCR (tracker)
Chile	-24.0	2680	0.14	0.3	20	0.6	0.4
Spain	39.9	1786	0.32	0.3	20	0.5	0.4
Sweden	57.8	1017	0.47	0.3	20	0.4	0.4

Fig. 9. AAL^G versus model parameters for the six different cases (three sites with two PV configurations, static and $1 \times p$) and the four IAM models considered in this paper.

Fig. 10. Range of values for parameters in different PV plants.

and (33). Interestingly, despite having originated at SANDIA, this study does not consider the IAM SANDIA model, which can be understood as another symptom of the obsolescence of this model.

We propose using these conversion equations to propagate the additional effect of soiling, which increases the angular loss and is only covered by the Martín-Ruiz model (by increasing the coefficient a_r , Eq. (10), to other models that do not include it. This is consistent with the recommended fitting of the Martín-Ruiz model from the experimental IAM curves mentioned above to, first, obtain the a_r coefficient for the clean module.

The equivalence between the ASHRAE and the physical model parameters has also been explored in [37].

5. AAL simulation exercises on real PV plants and model comparison

SISIFO is a PV simulation software (freely accessible at <https://sisifo.info>) developed by IES-UPM under the umbrella of several European projects: PVCROPS [38], MASLOWATEN [39] and currently PVOP [40]. The main models used in SISIFO for irradiance distribution, decomposition, transposition, and angular and spectral corrections were presented in 2013 [41] and can be found in [17,42–45]. SISIFO allows one to deal with mutual shading [46], different tracking types [47], and grid-connected and multi-pump PV systems. SISIFO has also has the ability to simulate bifacial PV arrays on sloped terrain [48].

Regarding the IAM models, until this work, SISIFO included the analytic version of the Martín-Ruiz model. Now, the following models have been added to the web version of SISIFO, under *Options > Angular*

Table 3
Comparison of IAM models in PV plants.

Chile								
IAM Model	One-axis tracking				Static			
	In-plane radiations in kWh/m ² :							
	$G_a = 3591$	$B_a = 3107$	$D_a = 452$	$R_a = 33$	$G_a = 2854$	$B_a = 2447$	$D_a = 401$	$R_a = 6$
	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R
ASHRAE ⁿ ($B_0 = 0.05$)	1.12	0.80	2.41	13.99	2.78	2.57	3.74	24.22
Air-glass ⁿ ($n = 1.526$)	0.97	0.54	2.59	19.64	2.92	2.63	4.13	37.38
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	1.03	0.61	2.63	19.10	2.95	2.67	4.15	37.05
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	1.00	0.61	2.45	19.10	2.93	2.67	4.03	34.63
Eye-sens ⁿ ($\Gamma = 1.1286$)	0.61	0.29	1.74	18.83	1.97	1.76	2.86	31.35
Spain								
IAM Model	One-axis tracking				Static			
	In-plane radiations in kWh/m ² :							
	$G_a = 2383$	$B_a = 1751$	$D_a = 606$	$R_a = 25$	$G_a = 1998$	$B_a = 1424$	$D_a = 568$	$R_a = 5$
	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R
ASHRAE ⁿ ($B_0 = 0.05$)	2.25	1.65	3.53	12.90	3.27	2.97	3.83	24.26
Air-glass ⁿ ($n = 1.526$)	2.26	1.53	3.73	18.04	3.53	3.13	4.21	37.36
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	2.31	1.58	3.77	17.54	3.55	3.15	4.22	37.01
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	2.25	1.58	3.56	17.54	3.50	3.15	4.08	34.64
Eye-sens ⁿ ($\Gamma = 1.1286$)	1.56	0.99	2.71	13.50	2.40	2.09	2.88	31.33
Sweden								
IAM Model	One-axis tracking				Static			
	In-plane radiations in kWh/m ² :							
	$G_a = 1355$	$B_a = 820$	$D_a = 517$	$R_a = 18$	$G_a = 1167$	$B_a = 657$	$D_a = 506$	$R_a = 4$
	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R	AAL ^G	AAL ^B	AAL ^D	AAL ^R
ASHRAE ⁿ ($B_0 = 0.05$)	2.99	2.02	4.22	11.58	3.82	3.37	4.20	24.24
Air-glass ⁿ ($n = 1.526$)	3.10	1.91	4.52	16.12	4.16	3.57	4.65	37.32
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	3.14	1.97	4.56	15.65	4.17	3.58	4.66	37.08
Mar-Ruiz ⁿ ($a_r = 0.17$)	3.04	1.97	4.30	15.65	4.09	3.58	4.50	34.61
Eye-sens ⁿ ($\Gamma = 1.1286$)	2.16	1.23	3.30	11.80	2.80	2.32	3.18	31.32

Loss Models (IAM), for both the front and rear sides: ASHRAE, Martín-Ruiz (numerical version), Eye-sensitivity, and Fresnel Air-glass. To do this, we first generate two-dimensional maps for $F_{B,F}$ (function of θ and the fitting parameter), $F_{D,F}$, $F_{R,F}$, and F_{HB} (functions of β and the fitting parameter) corresponding to each model, as presented in Section 3 and Fig. 3. Since these maps are independent of the location and configuration of the PV plant, we solved them once and included the resulting maps in SISIFO. In addition, analytical functions to obtain the AOI correction factors for the Martín-Ruiz Eqs. (22) and (23) and air-glass Eq. (25) models have also been included. It is worth mentioning that this full range of IAM calculation capabilities has been included in the open version of SISIFO to facilitate further research and model intercomparison.

Two comments on the implementation of IAM correction factors are opportune. On the one hand, the open version of SISIFO calculates D^{ISO} at a point only, the central point, of a generic row of a PV array and considers that the front row hides a portion of the sky characterized by an angle β_{HS} , as shown in Fig. 8. Thus, the viewing angle of the sky, shown in grey in the figure, is the same as if the row were alone and tilted at an angle $(\beta + \beta_{HS})$, which is exactly the one called by SISIFO to select the value $F_{D,F}$. On the other hand, Eq. (19) for calculating $F_{R,F}$ implicitly assumes that the light reflected from the ground is isotropic, while the ground in a multirow PV array exhibits shaded and unshaded areas. However, R_F is typically very small, so the error in the energy yield due to the use of $F_{R,F}$ according to Eq. (19) must also be very small. For the calculation of R_R in the bifacial modules, the more accurate and complex approach mentioned in Section 3 is implemented.

To understand the impact of IAM losses and the validity of different IAM models, we performed a comprehensive simulation exercise. In an effort to be representative, we have analyzed annual in-plane IAM front

radiation losses, referred to as AAL (Annual Angular Losses), at three sites of different latitudes (see Table 2) and two types of monofacial PV arrays: static and horizontal single-axis with activated back-tracking. The main characteristics of the simulated PV generators are given in Table 2.

The Typical Meteorological Year for each site was obtained from PVGIS. Note that, ρ and GCR influence the calculation of the irradiance components D_F^{ISO} and R_F^{ground} . We have simulated the case of perfectly clean modules. By turning off the spectral correction, the difference between global and effective radiations is only the IAM loss. The horizontal brightening component has been ignored because in the case of large multirow PV arrays on horizontal terrain, it is hidden by the preceding row. The model parameters have the following ranges: $0.007 \leq b_0 \leq 0.045$ (ASHRAE); $1.1 \leq n \leq 1.7$ (Air-glass); $0.11 \leq a_r \leq 0.18$ (Martín-Ruiz); $1.10 \leq \Gamma \leq 1.16$ (Eye-sensitivity).

Fig. 9 shows the evolution of global radiation losses, AAL^G , as a function of the model parameters sweep. In all cases, the numerical solutions for $F_{D,F}$ and $F_{R,F}$ have been considered. Again, the relatively low sensitivity of AAL to the model parameters is evident. In each case, the yellow and red horizontal bands indicate the $\pm 0.1\%$ and $\pm 0.2\%$, respectively, AAL^G ranges around the values calculated with the Air-glass model for the widely accepted default values of n for bare and AR-coated glass, 1.526 and 1.29, respectively. They help visualize the corresponding ranges of all the other-than- n parameters that lead to these AAL^G ranges. Fig. 9 reorganizes these results in an attempt to facilitate the identification of the parameters equivalent to $n = 1.29$ and $n = 1.526$. Note that there is no value for any parameter that matches the corresponding AAL^G results for $\pm 0.1\%$, but there is for $\pm 0.2\%$. With this in mind, the vertical lines in Fig. 10 indicate the proposed default values of this article.

Fig. 11. Annual angular energy losses in global (AAL^G), beam (AAL^B), diffuse (AAL^D) and reflected (AAL^R) components for each IAM Model and for each PV plant studied in this article.

The ranges of the parameters are shown in the Appendix of the models corresponding to the AAL^G range of $\pm 0.1\%$ and $\pm 0.2\%$ around the AAL^G value calculated with the Air-glass, ASHRAE, Martín-Ruiz, and Eye-sensitivity models. Detailed calculations of the various AAL for each irradiance component are shown in Table 3, indicated by the superscript. The values of AAL are given in percentage with two decimal places, in order to allow a better comparison between the different models. The reader should be aware that only the first digit is significant. This time, analytical approximations for $F_{D,F}$ and $F_{R,F}$ Eqs. (22) and (23) have also been considered. Related comments are as follows.

- Depending on the latitude and type of PV array, AAL^G follows the expected order: $AAL^B < AAL^D < AAL^R$ as can be seen in Fig. 11.
- The proposed analytical approximations for the diffuse irradiance correction factors closely match the detailed numerical solutions.
- The Air-glass model, with respect to the Martín-Ruiz model, tends to overestimate the annual angular loss for direct and reflected irradiance and to underestimate the loss for isotropic diffuse irradiance.
- The eye sensitivity model results in a significantly lower AAL than all other models. Considering that other models have been tested in the literature, its application may result in an overestimation of the energy yield.
- The Martín-Ruiz model, as already mentioned, is the only one that allows the calculation of the additional annual angular loss caused by soiling. As a reference, for a 2% loss in perpendicular irradiance due to soiling, this model estimates an additional AAL of 0.5%, 0.9% and 1.2% for single-axis tracking in Chile, Spain, and Sweden, respectively, and 1.0%, 1.3%, 1.7% for static PV generators, respectively. This strengthens our proposal to incorporate this additional loss in other models that do not cover it.

6. Conclusions

IAM refers to the light transmittance through the PV module to the solar cells relative to the normal incidence. The modeling of IAM versus the angle of incidence θ for clean modules has been reviewed. In chronological order of publication, the following parametric $IAM(\theta)$ models have been described: ASHRAE (1966), Air-glass (1996), Martín-Ruiz (2001), SANDIA (2004), Physical (2006) and Eye-sensitivity (2024). The description is self-contained in such a way that the interested reader can incorporate any of these models without having to consult other references.

In the search for their implementation in current PV software, two of these models have been disregarded: SANDIA model, because its corresponding database is no longer supported; and the Physical model, because its increase in complexity compared to the Air-glass model is not justified (differences between the two models are as small as 0.02%). All others have been implemented in SISIFO, an open PV software developed by the IES-UPM, so that they can be compared in terms of angle-of-incidence corrected radiation and energy yield losses. The Air-glass model is the one that PVsyst, probably the most widely used software for energy yield estimates today, implements, while SISIFO only focused on the Martín-Ruiz model until this work. The ability to directly handle experimental IAM curves, fit the Martín-Ruiz model parameter, incorporate soiling effects, and parameter conversion to apply other IAM models has also been implemented in SISIFO. The simulation of PV energy yield requires AOI correction factors for directional (direct and circumsolar) and diffuse (reflected from the sky, reflected from the ground, and horizon brightening) irradiance components. The latter are derived by integrating $IAM(\theta)$ over the corresponding angular extent seen by the PV module. These integrals are functions only of the module tilt and the model parameters. Therefore, they can be solved numerically once, and the derived 2D matrix results can be incorporated into PV simulation software packages. A review of some published analytical alternatives for some correction factors providing a direct solution instead of solving the integrals, has been done. Again, in chronological order of publication: Martín-Ruiz (2001), Marion (2017), Wright (2019) and Xie (2022). The Martín-Ruiz and the 2017 formulation for Air-glass have also been included in SISIFO for model intercomparison purposes. The adjustment of the model parameters was first addressed by minimizing the residuals between the experimental and modeled $IAM(\theta)$ values. Some models are difficult to adjust by this procedure because the residual curves are quite flat near the minimum. Then, an extensive energy yield simulation performed with SISIFO for three sites of different latitude and for static and one-axis tracked PV arrays allowed us to analyze in depth the relationship between model parameters and AAL, and to derive default values for the parameters of all the models, for PV modules covered with bare glass and AR-coated glass.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Grants PID2023-148369OB-C41 and PREP2023-001767 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU and ESF+.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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